

The importance of electric field in ions convergence and formation of sporadic E (Es) at the equatorial region

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ABSTRACT

The importance of electric field in formation of sporadic E (Es) at the equatorial region is investigated both analytically and numerically. In the suggested theory, the electric field in the lower thermosphere of the equatorial region is competitive to the effects of neutral wind direction, value and shear on ions vertical convergence into Es type high density thin layer. We show analytically that minimal negative values of vertical changes of the ions vertical drift velocity, which are necessary for ions convergence into a Es type layer, is possible due to electric field.

We also noted the importance of the electric field value and direction (including its components) in formation of the sporadic E. The electric field, even it is homogeneous in the region of ions convergence, can cause ions convergence into a Es type thin layer. The possibility of formation of the Es layer is demonstrated numerically in cases of presence of electric field with the zonal components.

We used the HWM14 data which also showed the importance of competitive effects of the electric field and neutral wind velocity in formation of the Es layers. Here it is also noted the decrease of the electric field effect and increase of the neutral wind (including zonal and meridional winds) factor from equatorial to mid-latitude regions.

The electric field also has an influence on the competitive roles of itself and the neutral wind in ions divergence. In the suggested theoretical model, the arbitrary wind velocity profile (including the vertical component), caused by atmospheric waves, can be taken into account. The possibility of theoretical prediction of the ions convergence/divergence processes at the regions, where they develop, shows that it is important to investigate the global distribution of molecular and heavy metallic ions in the lower thermosphere.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sporadic E(Es) will occur both at mid-latitudes and in the lower thermosphere of the equatorial and polar regions (Whitehead, 1989; Mathews, 1998). Es layers observed in equatorial areas are not always localized in the region of zonal neutral wind polarization change (Abdu et al., 2003), as defined by the windshear theory (Haldoups, 2012 and references therein). This indicates that there is an additional mechanism of convergence of ions in the Es type layer in the equatorial region, which may be caused by the presence of an electric field.

The vertical ion drift (EB drift) caused by the electric field in the equatorial region is important for studying the behavior of ions/electrons in the E and F regions of the ionosphere. Therefore, the electric field can influence the formation and localization of Es layers in the lower thermosphere.

The presented studies will show that the electric field in the equatorial lower thermosphere can cause the existence of a minimum negative value in the vertical change of the vertical drift velocity of ions. This condition can be fulfilled even when the electric field is constant and leads to the development of the process of convergence of ions and electrons into a narrow layer (convergence instability) and thus the formation of a high density narrow Es type layer is possible.

By analytical and appropriate numerical methods, the formation and localization of Es layers in the height regions of 90-150 km of the equatorial lower thermosphere will be shown. Along with the electric field, the presence of the neutral wind will be considered. Zonal and meridional components of its velocity are determined by the HWM14 data.

Sporadic E contains mainly metallic ions and the development of its formation mechanism, taking into account the presence of electric field, in addition to the realistic wind velocity height profile, is important to study their global and regional distributions.

2. THEORY AND NUMERICAL RESULTS OF SPORADIC E(ES) FORMATION AT EQUATORIAL REGION

The behavior of ions in the equatorial region resulting in the formation of the sporadic E(ES) layer, is significantly determined by the combined action of their collision with neutrals and the Lorentz force (Whitehead, 1989 and references therein), as well as their drift caused by the presence of electric field. It is also important, that the density of the Es layer can be controlled by the ions ambipolar diffusion. Here development of ions convergence processes also depends on their initial distribution. Considering these factors, the conditions for the development of the convergence of ions into a narrow layer can be obtained from the behavior of their density profile $N_i(z, t)$. By solving the continuity equation of ions in the analytical approach (Didebulidze et al., 2020; Dalakishvili et al., 2020), $N_i(z, t)$ has the following form:

$$N_e(z, t) \approx N_{om} \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{2D}{H_{ic}^2} + \frac{\partial w_{EN}}{\partial z} \right) (t - t_o) - \left(\frac{z - [z_{om} + w_{EN}(t - t_o)]}{H_{ic}} \right)^2 \right\}, \quad (1)$$

Here the small variations of ions drift velocity (w_{EN}) vertical changes $\partial w_{EN} / \partial z$ during time $t - t_o \ll H_{ic}^2 / 2D$ are assumed. H_{ic} is the characteristic scale height of ions which at some initial time $t = t_o$ determines the main ion/electron layer thickness ($2H_{ic}$) and the height region $z - z_{om} = \pm H_{ic}$, where their density decreases e-times. $H_{ic}^2 / 2D$ is the characteristic time of the ion density decrease by their diffusion ($\propto D$).

Equation (1) of ion/electron $N_e(z, t)$ density (assuming $N_i = N_e$) describes the evolution of their Gaussian type distribution, which at the initial time $t = t_o$, has maximal density (peak density) N_{om} at height $z = z_{om}$ (initial peak height). When $\left(-\frac{\partial w_{EN}}{\partial z}\right)_{\max} > \frac{2D}{H_{ic}^2}$, then Equation (1) shows a tendency of formation of high density Es type layer of ion/electron ($\frac{N_m(t > t_o)}{N_{om}} > 1$). The peak height of this layer $z = z_{om} + w_{EN}(t - t_o)$ moves upward ($w_{EN} > 0$) or downward ($w_{EN} < 0$) by ions vertical drift velocity w_{EN} and it could be localized at the height region with $w_{EN} = 0$. When $\left(\frac{\partial w_{EN}}{\partial z}\right)_{\max} > 0$, according to the Equation (1), at the region of ion drift velocity node the ion/electron density depletion ($\frac{N_m(t > t_o)}{N_{om}} < 1$) occurs.

The effect of electric field $\mathbf{E}(E_x, E_y, E_z)$ and neutral wind velocity $\mathbf{V}_n(V_x, V_y, V_z)$ on ions motion is included in its vertical drift velocity w_{EN} (Dalakishvili et al., 2020). We take a right-handed set of coordinates (x, y, z) with x directed to the magnetic north, y to the west and z vertically upward.

Hereafter the vertical coordinate z represents the residual between some actual h and initial heights h_o ($z = h - h_o$). The Equation (1) shows a tendency of formation of an Es type high density narrow layer for a short time interval. In order to assess the role of electric field in the process of ion convergence and formation of sporadic E we present numerically (Didebulidze et al., 2020; Dalakishvili et al., 2020) the behavior of ions/electrons for whole nights ($t - t_o \leq 12h$). In the first stage, we show only the effect of electric field. Further, we will consider its existence in the horizontal wind, whose meridional and zonal velocity profiles are determined by HWM14 data (Drob et al., 2015). In the presented simulation, the neutral particle densities of the lower thermosphere are used from the NRLMSISE-00 model (Picone et al., 2002), for the equatorial ($7^\circ \pm 2^\circ N, 45^\circ \pm 2^\circ E; I = 0 \pm 2^\circ$) and close to mid-latitude regions ($30^\circ \pm 2^\circ N, 45^\circ \pm 2^\circ E; I = 45^\circ \pm 2^\circ$).

Figure 1 shows that the zonal electric field (e.g. $E_y = 2\text{mV/m}$) can form Es layer even it is constant (panels a and d). In this case the ion/electron convergence processes start at around 121-122km height, where ion neutral collision frequency is equal to ion cyclotron frequency, and Es type high density ($N_{em} / N_{om} \approx 10$) narrow layer descends and localizes at the region where ion vertical drift velocity vanishes $w_{EN} \rightarrow 0$. Neglecting the presence of neutral wind effect, the same zonal electric field can also form Es type layer at mid-latitudes (e.g., $30^\circ N$), but with relatively smaller density ($N_{em} / N_{om} \approx 8.6$).

Electron density $N_e(h, t)/N_{om}$

Figure 1. The behavior of the ion/electron density $N_e(z, t)/N_{om}$ at: **(a, b, c)** the equatorial region with $I=0$ (7° N; 45° E) in case of **(a)** presence of zonal electric field with westward component $E_y=2\text{mV/m}$, **(b)** zonal wind with velocity determined by HWM14 data (day 102) and **(c)** presence of both electric field and zonal wind; **(d, e, f)** mid-latitudes with $I=45^\circ$ (30° N; 45° E) in case of **(d)** presence of only electric field with $E_y=2\text{mV/m}$, **(e)** horizontal wind with zonal and meridional velocities determined by HWM14 data and **(f)** presence of both electric field and horizontal wind.

Figure 1 shows also that only neutral wind can as well form Es type layer ($N_{em} / N_{om} > 1$) in equatorial (panel b) and mid-latitude regions (panel e). In this case the dominant effect in formation of Es layer at the equatorial region is caused by zonal wind, while at mid-latitudes both the meridional and zonal wind effects are important. In these cases, using the HWM14 data of one day (102), the presence of meridional and zonal wind components also results in formation of sporadic E with double peak below about 100km height.

Figure 1 demonstrates the importance of presence of electric field and neutral wind in the formation of Es layers at an equatorial (panel c), as well as mid-latitude (panel f) regions. In this case when electric field and the horizontal wind velocities are determined by HWM14 data, the density of a formed Es layer at the equatorial region (panel c) is higher ($N_{em} / N_{om} \approx 40$) than it was during only electric field (panel a - $N_{em} / N_{om} \approx 10$) and horizontal wind (panel b - $N_{em} / N_{om} \approx 3.7$). The presence of electric field at mid-latitude regions can influence formation of additional Es layer, e.g. at the height around 115km (panel f), which was not formed during the presence of only meridional and zonal winds (panel f).

So, the presence of electric field in equatorial region is important for formation of the Es layer as well as for its localization and density. In this case the oppositely directed electric field is also important, which influences the development of ion/electron divergence processes and can destroy the Es type layer, formation of which was possible during horizontal wind. The latter we do not demonstrate for brevity. Here it is also important an influence of vertical wind velocity and vertical electric field on ions vertical drift, which result in development of ion/electron convergence processes and leading to formation and localization of Es type layer.

The high density Es type layers, like given in Figures 1c and 1f, result in quick quenching of molecular ions (e.g., NO+, O2+) and dominance of metallic ions (Fe+, Mg+). The presence of convergence regions characteristic for lower thermosphere determined by electric field, as well as by realistic (three-dimensional) wind profile is important to study the molecular and metallic ions global distribution.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of the ion/electron density at the equatorial lower thermosphere and possibility of formation of sporadic E(Es) under the influence of electric field along with neutral wind, have been shown. In this case, the presence of a minimal negative value of the vertical change of vertical drift velocity of ions ($\partial w_{EN} / \partial z$) min < 0 in the lower thermosphere, as the main condition for predicting the formation of the Es layer (Didebulidze et al., 2020; Dalakishvili et al., 2020), was extended analytically and with appropriate numerical methods, in case of presence of the electric field in the equatorial region.

The importance of the electric field value and direction (including its components) in formation of the sporadic E has been noted. The electric field, even it is homogeneous in the region of ions

convergence, can cause ions convergence into a Es type thin layer. The possibility of formation of the Es layer is demonstrated numerically in case of presence of electric field.

We used the HWM14 data which also showed the importance of competitive effects of the electric field and neutral wind velocity in formation and localization of the Es layers (Figures 1c and 1f). The decrease of the zonal electric field effect and increase of the meridional and zonal winds factor in the ion total convergence from equatorial to mid-latitude regions, has been shown.

In the presented theoretical model, the realistic profile of the wind velocity and taking into account the electric field, are important for prediction of the regions of the ion convergence and formation of Es layers, as well as the regions of ion depletion. Therefore, it is important to study the global and regional distributions of the main molecular and metal ions that make up it in the lower thermosphere.

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